

Food security in developing countries: A review

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Abstract

Food security is a condition related to the ongoing availability of food. Finally, it is important to bear in mind that "climate change" has become such a dominating issue in economic analysis and policy making that other, not much less important issues such as ecosystem services, biodiversity, water management or social issues run the risk of being neglected or de-linked from the climate nexus. There is therefore a risk that governments and the international community optimize "climate mitigation and adaptation" without seeing (despite all synergies) the trade-off and conflicts with other issues.

Concerns over food security have existed throughout history. There is evidence of granaries being in use over 10,000 years ago, with central authorities in Civilizations including Ancient China and Ancient Egypt being known to release food from storage in times of famine. For a large number of developing countries, agriculture remains the single most important sector. Climate change has the potential to damage irreversibly the natural resource base on which agriculture depends, with grave consequences for food security. However, agriculture is the Sector that has the potential to transcend from being a problem to becoming an essential part of the solution to climate change provided there is a more holistic vision of food security. Agricultural mitigation, climate-change adaptation and agriculture's pro-poor development contribution. Many countries experience ongoing food shortages and distribution problems.

These result in chronic and often widespread hunger amongst significant numbers of people. Human population can respond to chronic hunger and malnutrition by decreasing body size, known in medical terms as stunting or stunted growth. This process starts in utero if the mother is malnourished and continues through approximately the third year of life. The required transformation is much more profound to bear in mind that "climate change" has become such a dominant issue in economic analysis and policy making that other, not much less important issues such as ecosystem services, bio-diversity water management or social issues run the risk of being neglected or de-linked from the climate nexus. There is therefore a risk that governments and the international community optimize "climate mitigation and adaptation" without seeing (despite all synergies) the trade-offs and conflicts with other issues.

Introduction

Food security is a condition related to the ongoing availability of food (Robert 2004). Concerns over food Security has existed throughout history. There is evidence of granaries being in use over 10,000 years ago, with central authorities in Civilizations including Ancient China and Ancient Egypt being known to release food from storage in times of famine. Yet it was only at the 1974 World Food Conference that the term food security was established as a formal concept. Originally, food security was understood to apply at the national level, with a state being food secure when there was sufficient food to sustain a steady expansion of food consumption and to offset fluctuations in production and prices". A new definition emerged at 1996 World Food Summit, this time with the emphasis being on

individuals enjoying food security, rather than the nation.

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO 2009), food security "exists when all people, at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food to meet their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life".

Household food security exists when all members at all times, have access to enough food for an active, healthy life. Individuals who are food secure do not live in hunger or fear of starvation. Food insecurity, on the other hand, is a situation of "limited or uncertain availability of nutritionally adequate and safe food or limited or uncertain ability to acquire acceptable foods in socially acceptable ways",

according to the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) The FAO identified the four pillars of food security as availability, access, utilization, and stability. The United Nations (UN) recognized the Right to food in the Declaration of Human Rights in 1948, and has since noted that it is vital for the enjoyment of all other rights.

World Summit on Food Security

The World Summit on Food Security held in Rome in 1996, aimed to renew a global commitment to the fight against hunger. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO 1997) called the summit in response to widespread under-nutrition and growing concern about the capacity of agriculture to meet future food needs. The conference produced two key documents, the Rome Declaration on World Food Security and the World Food Summit Plan of Action.

The Rome Declaration calls for the members of the United Nations to work to halve the number of chronically undernourished people on the Earth by the year 2015. The Plan of Action sets a number of targets for government and non-governmental organizations for achieving food security, at the individual, household, national, regional and global levels.

Another World Summit on Food Security took place in Rome between November 16 and 18, 2009. The decision to convene the summit was taken by the Council of FAO in June 2009, at the proposal of FAO Director General Dr Jacques Diouf Heads of State and Government attended the summit, which took place at the FAO's headquarters.

The State of Food Security in the World

About 850 million people in the world are undernourished - a number that has hardly changed since the 1990-92 base period for the World Food Summit and Millennium Development Goal commitments on reducing hunger by half by 2015. Of particular concern are hunger hotspots, marked by the widespread persistence and prevalence of food insecurity, especially in protracted crises. As of May 2006, 39 countries in the world were experiencing serious food emergencies and required external assistance for dealing with critical food insecurity: 25 in Africa, 11 in Asia and Near East, 2 in Latin

America and 1 in Europe. Table 1 clearly indicates the importance of human agency in inducing crises, either directly through wars and civil strife) or through interaction with natural hazards that would otherwise have been of minor importance.

Table 1. Food emergencies, 2005

Dominant variable	Asia	Africa	Latin America	Europe	Total
Human	3	10	1	1	15
Natural	7	8	1	0	16
Combined	1	7	0	0	8
Total	11	25	2	1	39

Source: FAO VIEWS:2005

FAO Policy Priorities for Food Security

FAO's twin-track approach' for fighting hunger combines sustainable agricultural and rural development with targeted programmes for enhancing direct access to food for the most needy the first track addresses recovery measures for establishing resilient food systems. Factors that affect food system resilience include the structure of the food economy as a whole, as well as its Components such as agricultural production, technology, the diversification of food processing, markets and consumption. Track 2 assesses the options for providing support to vulnerable groups.

Vulnerability analysis offers a forward looking way of understanding food security dynamics, calling for explicit attention to risk and the options for managing it. Both tracks are intended to be mutually reinforcing, and the positive interaction between them should reinforce the path to recovery. For example, managing risks goes beyond assisting those affected by a particular shock in addressing their immediate food needs. A range of options are available for addressing longer term food security through sustainable agricultural and rural development aimed at preventing or mitigating risk.

The WHO (2013) states that there are three pillars that determine food security: food availability, food access, and food use. The FAO adds a fourth pillar: the stability of the first three dimensions of food security over time. In 2009, the World Food Summit (2009) on Food Security stated that the "four pillars of food security are availability, access, utilization, and stability "Food security exists when all people, at all times, have physical and economic

access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life" (World Food Summit, 1996).

From this definition, **four main dimensions or pillars of food security can be identified:**

Physical availability of food

Food availability addresses the supply side" of food security and is determined by the level of food production, stock levels and net trade. (a)

Economic and physical access to food

An adequate supply of food at the national or international level does not in itself guarantee. House hold level food security. Concerns about insufficient food access have resulted in a greater policy focus on incomes, expenditure, markets and prices in achieving food security objectives.

Food Utilization

Utilization is commonly understood as the way the body makes the most of various nutrients in the food. Sufficient energy and nutrient intake by individuals is the result of good care and feeding practices, food preparation, diversity of the diet and intra-household distribution of food. Combined with good biological utilization of food consumed, this determines the nutritional status of individuals."

Stability of the other three dimensions over time

Even if your food intake is adequate today, you are still considered to be food insecure if you have inadequate access to food on a periodic basis, risking a deterioration of your nutritional status. Adverse weather conditions, political instability, or economic factors (unemployment, rising food prices) may have an impact on your food security status.

Effects of food insecurity

"Famine and hunger are both rooted in food insecurity. Chronic food insecurity translates into a high degree of vulnerability to famine and hunger; ensuring food security presupposes elimination of that vulnerability."

Many countries experience ongoing food shortages and distribution problems. These result in chronic and often widespread hunger amongst significant numbers of people. Human populations can respond to chronic hunger and malnutrition by

decreasing body size, known in medical terms as stunting or stunted growth. This process starts in utero if the mother is malnourished and continues through approximately the third year of life. It leads to higher infant and child mortality, but at rates for lower than during famines. Once stunting has occurred, improved nutritional intake after the age of about two years is unable to reverse the damage. Stunting itself can be viewed as a coping mechanism, bringing body size into alignment with the calories available during adulthood in the location where the child is born. Limiting body size as a way of adapting to low levels of energy (calories) adversely affect health in three ways:

- Premature failure of vital organs during adulthood. For example, a 50-year-old individual might die of heart failure because his/her heart suffered structural defects during early development,
- Stunted individuals suffer a higher rate of disease and illness than those who have not undergone stunting:
- Severe malnutrition in early childhood often leads to defects in cognitive development.

When analyzing food insecurity, it is not enough to know the duration of the problem that people are experiencing, but also how intense or severe the impact of the identified problem is on the overall food security and nutrition status, This knowledge will influence the nature, extent and the assistance needed by affected population groups. It is important to understand how these three concepts are related to food insecurity.

Hunger is usually understood as an uncomfortable or painful sensation caused by insufficient food energy consumption. Scientifically, hunger is referred to as food deprivation. Simply put, all hungry people are food insecure, but not all food insecure people are hungry, as there are other causes of food insecurity, including those due to poor intake of micronutrients (Borlaug 2000).

Malnutrition results from deficiencies, excesses or imbalances in the consumption of macro- and/or micronutrients. Malnutrition may be an outcome of food insecurity, or it may relate to non-

food factors, such as:

- inadequate care practices for children,
- insufficient health services; and
- an unhealthy environment.

While poverty is undoubtedly a cause of hunger, lack of adequate and proper nutrition itself is an underlying cause of poverty. A current and widely used definition of poverty is: "Poverty encompasses different dimensions of deprivation that relate to human capabilities including consumption and food security, health, education, rights, voice, security, dignity and decent work".

Challenges to achieving food security

- Global water crisis
- Land degradation and Desertification
- Land deal and Land grabbing
- Climate change and agriculture
- Agricultural diseases
- Dictatorship and kleptocracy (Political corruption)
- Food sovereignty

Risks to food security

Population growth

Current UN projections show a continued increase in population in the near future (but a steady decline in the population growth rate), with the global population expected to reach between 8.3 and 10.9 billion by 2050. UN Population Division estimates for the year 2150 range between 3.2 and 24.8 billion; mathematical modeling supports the lower estimate. Some analysts have questioned the sustainability of further world population growth, highlighting the growing pressures on the environment global food supplies, and energy resources. Solutions for feeding the nine billion in the future are being studied and documented. One out of every seven people on our planet go to sleep hungry. People are suffering due to overpopulation, 25,000 people die of malnutrition and hunger related diseases every day.

Fossil fuel dependence

While agricultural output increased as a result of the Green Revolution, the energy input into the process that is, the energy that must be expended to

produce a crop has also increased at a greater rate, so that the ratio of crops produced to energy input has decreased over time. Green Revolution techniques also heavily rely on chemical fertilizers, pesticides and herbicides, some of which must be developed from fossil fuels, making agriculture increasingly reliant on petroleum products.

Between 1950 and 1984, as the Green Revolution transformed agriculture around the globe, world grain production increased by 250%. The energy for the Green Revolution was provided by fossil fuels in the form of fertilizers (natural gas), pesticides (oil), and hydrocarbon fueled irrigation.

The authors of this study believe that the mentioned agricultural crisis will only begin to impact us after 2020, and will not become critical until 2050. The oncoming peaking of global oil production and subsequent decline of production), along with the peak of North American natural gas production will very likely precipitate this agricultural crisis much sooner than expected. Geologist Dale Allen Pfeiffer claims that coming decades could see spiraling food prices without relief and massive starvation on a global level such as never experienced before.

Hybridization, genetic engineering and loss of biodiversity

In agriculture and animal husbandry, the Green Revolution popularized the use of conventional hybridization to increase yield by creating "high-yielding varieties" (Pollen 2001). Often the handful of hybridized breeds originated in developed countries and were further hybridized with local varieties in the rest of the developing world to create high yield strains resistant to local climate and diseases. Local governments and industry have been pushing hybridization which has resulted in several of the indigenous breeds becoming extinct or threatened. Disuse because of unprofitability and uncontrolled intentional and unintentional cross-pollination and crossbreeding (genetic pollution), formerly huge gene pools of various wild and indigenous breeds have collapsed causing widespread genetic erosion and genetic pollution (Claudio 2006). This has resulted in loss of genetic diversity and biodiversity as a whole. genetically modified organism (GMO) is an organism whose genetic material has been altered using the genetic engineering techniques generally known as

recombinant DNA technology Genetically Modified (GM) crops today have become a common source for genetic pollution, not only of wild varieties but also of other domesticated varieties derived from relatively natural hybridization. LESIONS a review of Borlaug's 2000 publication entitled Ending world hunger the promise of biotechnology and the threat of antiscience zealotry, the authors argued that Borlaug's warnings were still true in 2010,

GM crops are as natural and safe as today's bread wheat, opined Dr. Borlaug, who also reminded agricultural scientists of their moral obligation to stand up to the anti-science crowd and warn policy makers that global food insecurity will not disappear without this new technology and ignoring this reality global food insecurity would make future solutions all the more difficult to achieve.

Intellectual property rights

There is much debate on whether IPRs hurt or harm independent development in terms of agriculture and food production. Hartman Meyer and Annette von Lossau describe both sides of the issue, while saying "Among scholars, the thesis that the impetus to self-determined development and the protection of intellectual property go hand in hand is disputed - to put it mildly. Many studies have concluded that there is virtually no positive correlation between establishing self-sustained economic growth and ensuring protection of intellectual property

Price setting

On April 30, 2008. Thailand, one of the world's biggest rice exporters, announces the project of the creation of the Organization of Rice Exporting Countries with the potential to develop into a price-fixing cartel for rice. It is a project to organize 21 rice exporting countries to create a homonymous organization to control the price of rice. The group is mainly made up of Thailand, Vietnam, Cambodia, Laos and Myanmar. The organization attempts to serve the purpose of making a "contribution to ensuring food stability, not just in an individual country but also to address food shortages in the region and the world". However, it is still questionable whether this organization will serve its role as an effective rice price fixing cartel, that is similar to OPEC's mechanism for managing

petroleum. Economic analysts and traders said the proposal would go nowhere because of the inability of governments to cooperate with each other and control farmers' output. Moreover, countries that are involved expressed their concern, that this could only worsen the food security.

Children and food security

April 29, 2008, a UNICEF UK report found that the world's poorest and most vulnerable children are being hit the hardest by the impact of climate change. The report, "Our Climate, Our Children, Our Responsibility: The Implications of Climate Change for the World's Children," says access to clean water and food supplies will become more difficult, particularly in Africa and Asia.

By way of comparison, in one of the largest food producing countries in the world, the United States, approximately one out of six people are "food insecure", including 17 million children, according to the US Department of Agriculture A 2012 study in the Journal of Applied Research on Children found that rates of food security varied significantly by race, class and education. In both kindergarten and third grade, 8% of the children were classified as food insecure, but only 5% of white children were food insecure, while 12% and 15% of black and Hispanic children were food insecure, respectively. In third grade, 13% of black and 11% of Hispanic children are food insecure compared to 5% of white children.

Gender and food security

Gender inequality both leads to and is a result of food insecurity. According to estimates women and girls make up 60% of the world's chronically hungry and little progress has been made in ensuring the equal right to food for women enshrined in the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women." Women face discrimination both in education and employment opportunities and within the household, where their bargaining power is lower. On the other hand, gender equality is described as instrumental to ending malnutrition and hunger. Women tend to be responsible for food preparation and childcare within the family and are more likely to be spent their income on food and their children's needs. Women also play an important role in food production,

processing, distribution and marketing. They often work as unpaid family workers, are involved in subsistence farming and represent about 43% of the agricultural labor force in developing countries, varying from 20% in Latin America to 30% in Eastern and Southeastern Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. However, women face discrimination in access to land, credit, technologies, finance and other services.

Finally, it is important to bear in mind that "climate change" has become such a dominating issue in economic analysis and policy making that other, not much less important issues such as ecosystem services, biodiversity, water management or social issues run the risk of being neglected or de-linked from the climate nexus. There is therefore a risk that governments and the international community optimize "climate mitigation and adaptation" without seeing (despite all synergies) the trade-offs and conflicts with other issues.

POLICIES AND PROGRAMS FOR IMPROVING FOOD SECURITY

By the United Nations

The UN Millennium Development Goals are one of the initiatives aimed at achieving food security in the world. The first Millennium Development Goal states that the UN "is to eradicate extreme hunger and poverty" by 2015. This approach emphasizes the physical availability of food; the social economic and physical access people have to food; and the nutrition, safety and cultural appropriateness or adequacy of food,

By the Food and Agriculture Organization

The Food and Agriculture Association of the United Nations stated in The State of Food Insecurity in the World 2003 that countries that have reduced hunger often had rapid economic growth, specifically in their agricultural sectors. These countries were also characterized as Development Index At that time, the FAO considered addressing agriculture and population having slower population growth, lower HIV rates, and higher rankings in the Human growth vital to achieving food security. In The State of Food Insecurity in the World 2012, the FAO restated its focus on economic growth and agricultural growth to achieve food security and added a focus on the poor

and on nutrition-sensitive" growth. For economic and agricultural growth to be "nutrition-sensitive resources should be utilized to improve access to diverse diets for the poor as well as access to a safe water supply and to healthcare.

The FAO has proposed a twin track approach to fight food insecurity that combines sustainable development and short-term markets and rural infrastructure rennet , Development approaches include investing in rural " In general, the FAO proposes the use of public policies and programs that promote long-term economic growth that will benefit the poor. The FAO stated that "approaches should be human rights-based, target the poor, promote gender equality. enhance long-term resilience and allow sustainable graduation out of poverty.

World Food Day was established on October 16, in honor of the date that the FAO was founded (back in 1945). On this day, the FAO hosts a variety of event at the headquarters in Rome and around the world, as well as seminars with UN officials.

By the United States Agency for International Development

The United States Agency for International Development (USAID) proposes several key steps to increasing agricultural productivity which is in turn key to increasing rural income and reducing food insecurity. They include:

- Boosting agricultural science and technology. Current agricultural yields are insufficient to feed the growing population. Eventually, the rising agricultural productivity drives economic growth.
- Securing property rights and access to finance.
- Enhancing human capital through education and improved health.
- Conflict prevention and resolution mechanisms and democracy and governance based on principles of accountability and transparency in public institutions and the rule of law are basic to reducing vulnerable members of society.

Improving agricultural productivity to benefit the rural poor

There are strong, direct relationships between agricultural productivity, hunger, poverty, and sustainability. Three-quarters of the world's poor live in rural areas and make their living from agriculture. Hunger and child malnutrition are greater in these areas than in urban areas. Moreover, the higher the proportion of the rural population that obtains its income solely from subsistence farming (without the benefit of pro-poor technologies and access to markets), the higher the incidence of malnutrition. Therefore, improvements in agricultural productivity aimed (Gary *et al.* 2000). At small-scale farmers will benefit the rural poor first. Food and feed crop demand is likely to double in the next 50 years, as the global population approaches nine billion. Growing sufficient food will require people to make changes such as increasing productivity in areas dependent on rain fed agriculture, improving soil fertility management; expanding cropped areas; investing in Irrigation; conducting agricultural trade between countries, and reducing gross food demand by Influencing diets and reducing post-harvest losses

Researchers suggest forming an alliance between the emergency food program and community supported agriculture, as some countries' food stamps cannot be used at farmer's markets and places where food is less processed and grown locally. The gathering of wild food plants appears in poverty alleviation to be an efficient alternative method of subsistence in tropical countries, which may play a role.

Conclusion

For most developing countries, agriculture remains the key economic and social sector, which is of pivotal importance for assuring food security. Global warming has the potential to damage Reversibly the natural resources based on which agriculture depends, with grave consequences for food security, Climate change could reduce total agricultural production in many developing Countries by up to 50% in the next few decades, in particular in South Asia and sub Saharan Africa. At the same time, the population of these countries is projected to nearly

double, creating huge tensions between food supply and demand. Although food could be theoretically imported from temperate-zone countries that may benefit from global warming, this may simply be unaffordable given the huge demand, low purchasing power and expected food price increases.

The current structures in global agricultural input and output markets do not ease, but rather complicate the required fundamental transformation of agricultural production methods and consumption patterns. Huge price distortions, considerable externalities, market and policy failures, as well as powerful commercial interests create a "minefield" for constructive action being (unilaterally) undertaken at national level. Without a reform of international trade and investment policies that are really supportive of ecological agriculture national-level action may remain ineffective. There is generally too much emphasis on and simplistic overestimation of the potential of technological development for agricultural transformation. This will only give false hope and excuses for doing nothing really fundamental. In fact, as the above analysis shows, only few problems in agriculture are mainly caused by a lack of technology, many are related to social, economic and cultural issues that require structural changes, not techno-fixes (Paul *et al.*, 2009). It is therefore critical to first of all define what problems are best solved by changing legal frameworks, trade policies, incentive structure or human behaviour and, second, what contribution technology could make within this very context.

Finally, it is important to bear in mind that "climate change" has become such a dominating issue in economic analysis and policy making that other, not much less important issues such as ecosystem services, biodiversity, water management or social issues run the risk of being neglected or de-linked from the climate nexus. There is therefore a risk that governments and the international community optimize "climate mitigation and adaptation" without seeing (despite all synergies) the trade-offs and conflicts with other issues.

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